

Impact of English Language Teaching: A Critical Study

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Abstract:

The importance of teaching and learning English has increased significantly, as a result of the language's widespread usage and spread over the world. Many concerns about efficient English language instruction have been brought up by this. In this case, the Researcher elaborates on the various elements that contribute to good English language instruction using his personal experience teaching the language for over ten years. Effective English language instruction is a result of a variety of elements, including the teacher, teaching strategies, instructional resources, and the students themselves.

Keywords: Teaching and learning, Methods, Techniques, Approaches, Language.

Introduction:

As a result of globalization in recent decades, English has become a universal language. International trade, tourism, education, and diplomacy are all conducted in this language. In a similar vein, it has been established as a universal language. To participate in this worldwide society, one must be able to speak and understand English. The global demand for English language proficiency and its increasing distribution have led to a remarkable trend in English language learning. English language instruction is now widely implemented as a result of this incredible growth in language learning for many purposes. English language instruction is offered by numerous organizations and language schools all over the world. To ensure that students fulfill their objective of learning the English language, Effective English language instruction is required of the students. Without a question, teaching English well creates successful learning, yet

legitimate questions like "What is effective English language teaching and what makes it effective?" come up. Effective teaching is a multifaceted, complex process that has varied meanings for different individuals, making it challenging to define (Bell, 2005). Effectiveness is a hard concept to define, but we can sum it up by saying that it is the ability to successfully achieve a goal or intended result. Acheson and Gall 2003, as stated in Uygun, 2013: "Effective teaching entails the ability to provide instruction that helps the students develop different knowledge, skills, and understandings intended by curriculum objectives and students learn irrespective of their characteristics."

Learners acquire the English language more easily when it is taught well. That is to say, learners quickly acquire the ability to speak successfully in the English language. In an efficient English language education classroom, students show that they grasp meanings rather than just remembering information (Ghimire, 2019).

What Makes Teaching English a Successful Field?

The question of what constitutes effective teaching remains unresolved even after defining effective teaching in general and effective English language instruction in particular. There are a multitude of elements that contribute to the effectiveness of teaching English. All parties involved in English language instruction have a direct and/or indirect role in its effectiveness. The stakeholders include, among others, administrators, parents, teachers, and students. Having studied English for many years and taught it for ten years, I can attest that a variety of factors are essential to good English language instruction. Effective teaching, in my opinion, requires a teacher's personality, pedagogical and content knowledge, as well as the motivation, readiness, and activation of the students. Furthermore, for effective teaching in this day and age, teachers need to be knowledgeable about technology and up to date on the latest developments in English language instruction. In summary, I have covered four factors in this section: the teacher, the methods and techniques, the teaching materials, and the learners. Instructor Teachers play a crucial role in the success of English language instruction. English language teachers and instructors must be effective in order for English language instruction to be effective. The possession of various elements, such as curriculum knowledge, general pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge,

pedagogical content knowledge, and knowledge of knowledge of educational contexts, knowledge of learners and their characteristics, and knowledge of educational ends, purposes, and values (Clark & Walsh, 2002 as cited in Uygun, 2013). This demonstrates the need for teachers to possess socioemotional skills, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge. Stated differently, an effective teacher is one who possesses strong subject-matter expertise, a solid understanding of effective delivery methods and strategies, and a positive rapport with the students. Likewise, an enthusiastic, creative, tolerant, patient, kind, reasonable, open-minded, optimistic, flexible, and endowed with a good sense of humor are all necessary qualities for effective and dynamic constructive views toward novel concepts and a few other individual traits (Gimire, 2019). In this day and age, content and pedagogical knowledge alone, along with a few other mentioned personal attributes, is insufficient for teaching effectively. Given that we live in a scientific and technological age, education is greatly impacted by these two fields, just like other industries. The education sector in general and teaching and learning activities in particular cannot be an exception to the way that information and communication technology (ICT) has affected every aspect of human life. What ICT Is "...ICT is defined as..." claims Hafifah (2019, p. 21). as the processes of communicating, creating and disseminating, storing and managing information through the use of technologies, including computers, the internet, and other telecommunications media. ICT in education refers to the use of various ICT devices for teaching and learning. ICTs, or information and communication technologies, are being used in education to help students learn more efficiently by giving teachers access to a variety of innovative pedagogies (Dhital, 2018). The concept of literacy, student-teacher relationships, pedagogy, and student learning achievement has all altered as a result of the use of ICTs in education. Teaching and learning have changed for both teachers and students who were only exposed to traditional methods of instruction. It aids pupils in participating in this worldwide It aids pupils in competing in this international market. ICT in education improves learning, gives students new skills, makes teacher training easier and better, and lowers the costs related to providing traditional instruction (UNESCO, 2014). Therefore, for language instruction to be effective, teachers should be tech savvy. In addition to being able to use and incorporate ICT in language teaching, he or she should be ICT literate. Teachers must stay current with technological knowledge because it is constantly changing, more

so than pedagogical and content knowledge (Harris, Mishra & Koehler, 2009). In summary, for language instruction to be effective in this day and age, teachers need to be up to date on the latest developments in ICT and possess a solid understanding of ICT. In a similar vein, English language instructors ought to speak the language well. It does not follow that an English native speaker should be a teacher. Effective English language teachers can be anyone, even non-native speakers of the language. The instructor should be well-versed in the needs, interests, background, and level of each student. The ability to organize and make sense of the material, spark and maintain students' interest and motivation, be fair and accessible to them, and possess knowledge and proficiency of the target language are the coveted qualities of a successful second language instructor (Uygun, 2013). Additionally, a good English language instructor should impart phonological, grammatical, lexical, pragmatic, and sociocultural knowledge to their students in addition to being enthusiastic and clear in their instruction.

Approaches and Strategies

Effective English language instruction depends heavily on the teaching strategies and tactics employed in the classroom. The core of teaching-learning activities is frequently thought to be a method. It is the comprehensive strategy for the systematic delivery of language content. For effective teaching, a variety of techniques can be applied. A teacher should employ methods that are sensitive to context and culture, as the most effective strategies in one situation might not be in another. It implies that educators ought to apply the strategies and tactics that are founded on kumaravadivelu (2001) states that for language pedagogy to be effective, it must take into account the needs of a specific group of teachers instructing a specific group of students who are pursuing a specific set of objectives within a specific institutional context embedded in a specific sociocultural milieu (p. 538). Teachers should do this by using self-generated strategies that work best in their particular context. Teachers can develop such techniques with the aid of action research and reflective practice. Instructors must possess independence, dynamism, reflection, and intuition. To put it briefly, educators ought to apply their theories to their practice and their practice to their theory (Kumaravadivelu, 2001).

Instructional Resources

The teaching resources that language instructors employ in their classrooms are essential for providing effective instruction in the English language. Teachers rely on various materials to support their teaching and students' learning because the materials used in English language classrooms make instruction engaging and effective. Teaching materials, whether they are created independently or commercially, should take the needs, skill levels, and interests of the students into consideration. Content- and context-sensitive resources should be utilized in language learning environments. They should encourage learners to develop learning strategies and skills, foster interaction, and be generative in language use. Permit an emphasis on both form and function, provide chances for integrated language use, be genuine, and connect to one another to build a progression of abilities, comprehensions, and language items, be appealing, have clear directions, and be adaptable (Howard & Major, 2004).

Learner

Effective teaching is influenced by a variety of factors, one of which is the learner. In order to participate in the activities held both inside and outside of the classroom, students should be engaged and imaginative. A successful learner who sets and maintains goals is linked to an active and creative learner. Fulfills his personal objectives (Karen, 2001). In the words of Zamani and Ahangari (2016), "Good teaching is clearly important to raising student achievement, if teacher is not aware of the learner's expectation and needs related to the course, it will have negative outcomes regarding the students' performance" (p. seventy). In order to teach effectively, a teacher must encourage student participation and creativity. Giving students materials to collaborate with friends and take responsibility for the classroom activities is one way to encourage creativity and activity in the classroom. Such assignments should be given by teachers in order to foster both collaborative learning and learner autonomy.

Conclusion:

Based on the afore mentioned theories, it can be said that teaching English language requires a variety of factors in order to be effective. The most important prerequisite for teaching English language proficiency is having a competent teacher. To teach effectively, a teacher needs to have a solid understanding of the subject matter, pedagogy, technology, and socio-affective skills. It is

imperative that language teachers utilize context- and culture-sensitive materials and methods in the classroom, as the materials and methods prescribed by other experts may not be appropriate in every situation. The instructor should create resources and techniques for this that most effectively suits their environments with the aid of action research and thoughtful practice. Lastly, for teaching and learning to be effective, students need to be engaged and imaginative. To do this, educators should assign assignments that promote student autonomy and group projects.

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